

The Effect of Spices on Rice Weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*

(Linnaeus, 1763)

Cherry*

Abstract

The present study was conducted to know the effect of different spices on rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* in stored rice grains at the laboratory of Zoology Department, from July to December 2014. Under the laboratory conditions (28.4°C to 31°C and 80 to 97 percent relative humidity) the effectiveness of different spices (chili fruit *Capsicum anum*, pepper seed *Piper nigrum*, cinnamon bark *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, turmeric rhizome *Curcuma longa*, and lemongrass *Cymbopogon* sp.) was assessed by 30 adult rice weevils which were introduced into each plastic bottle containing 100g rice grains treated with 20g, 30g and 40g concentrations of respective spice powders. The mean mortality of rice weevil against the use of different spices is significantly different at $p < 0.05$ ($F = 20.127$). Probit analysis showed that the dose required to attain 50% mortality of rice weevil was lower in *Piper nigrum* ($LD_{50} = 0.74g$) than other spice powders. Twenty-eight days after treatment, the results revealed that the minimum mean number of rice weevils in rice grains treated with pepper had less weevils compared with the other treatments. This result suggests that pepper seeds are comparatively more effective in controlling rice weevil *S. oryzae* than using other spice powders.

Keywords: spices, rice weevil

Introduction

Insects are the major cause of loss of stored food. They cause losses in storing grains, especially cereals, in conditions favorable to their development 25-35°C and low RH (Batta, 2004). Order Coleoptera contains the largest number of species and, among them, there are some of the most important infestation of the stored products. In the family Curculionidae, genus *Sitophilus* are major stored product pests. Rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* is considered a primary stored-grain insect, and in Myanmar it is one of the most important storage pests, which causes severe damage to raw cereals throughout the world (Champ and Dyte, 1976). This species has a relatively short developmental period and high populations can easily be built up (Aitken, 1975). The effective control of stored grain pests has long been the aim of entomologists throughout the world. Synthetic chemical pesticides have been used for many years to control stored grain pests (Salem *et al.*, 2007). However, the heavy use of insecticides causes environmental pollution, and the reduction of natural enemies of insect pests and beneficial insects, increased concern by consumers over insecticide residues in processed cereal products, the occurrence of insecticide-resistant insect strains, the ecological consequences, increasing cost of application and the precautions necessary to work with traditional chemical insecticides, call for new approaches to control stored-product insect pests (Aslam *et al.*, 2002; Udo, 2005; Fields, 2006; Salem *et al.*, 2007; Mahdian and Rahman, 2008).

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Plants and plant products can affect insects and other storage pests in various ways. They may exhibit pest control activity as toxicants, attractants, repellents, antifeedants, and as growth regulators (Chomchalow, 2003). Therefore plant materials have been used in the control of storage pests in many parts of the world since ancient times. These are (i) spices, (ii) medicinal and other plants. Spices are dried seed, fruit, root, bark or vegetative substance used as a food additive for flavoring. The use of spices is less costly, easily available for the developing world, safer and do not cause hazards in the commodity (Aslam *et al.*, 2002; Mahdian and Rahman, 2008).

Previous research indicated that some plant powders, oils and extracts have strong effects on stored grain insects such as toxicity and the inhibition of reproduction (Emeasor *et al.*, 2005; Nadra, 2006).

Although the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* is a very serious pest of stored grain around the world (Nayak *et al.*, 2004), to the best of my knowledge very little information is available on the use of plant powders on the *Sitophilus oryzae* in local area. Therefore the present study was conducted with the following aim and objectives:

- to find out the potential of five spices (chili fruit *Capsicum annum*, pepper seed *Piper nigrum*, cinnamon bark *Cinnamomum zeylanicum*, turmeric rhizome *Curcuma longa*, and lemongrass *Cymbopogon* sp.) applied at different concentrations to control rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*
- to share the basic information about the effectiveness of spicy plant materials in the control of rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*

Materials and Methods

The control of *Sitophilus oryzae* in stored rice using different spices was conducted at the laboratory of Zoology Department, during June, 2014 to December, 2014. Rice grains were disinfested by keeping them in a refrigerator at -18°C for 24 hours before being used for experimental purposes. The adult rice weevils were collected from the infested rice and maintained in a plastic bottle containing disinfested rice. The culture was used throughout the period of experiments.

Capsicum anum (dry chili), *Piper nigrum* (pepper seed), *Cinnamomum zeylanicum* (cinnamon bark), *Curcuma longa* (rhizome of turmeric) and *Cymbopogon* sp. (lemongrass) were purchased from the market and grinded as fine powders. Each powder was packed into a muslin bag at 20 g, 30 g and 40 g concentrations respectively and placed into each plastic bottle containing 100g of rice while the control bottle did not have any powder. Sex randomly chosen, thirty numbers of *Sitophilus oryzae* collected from the culture were released into each respective plastic bottle. These bottles were placed in room temperature. Daily room temperature and related humidity were recorded by hygrometer and the number of dead weevils in each bottle was counted daily. Three replications per treatment of experiments were set up. The final adult populations were recorded after 28 days.

Rice weevil mortality was assessed as:

Number of dead insects / Total number of insects x 100

Data on percentage adult weevil mortality were corrected using Abbott's (1925) formula.

$$P_T = \frac{P_O - P_C}{100 - P_C}$$

where P_T = corrected mortality (%); P_O = observed mortality (%); P_C = control mortality (%).

Statistical analysis

Data obtained were subjected to analysis of variance (non-parametric ANOVA) and significant difference at $P < 0.05$ by using Kruskal-Wallis Test-SPSS version 20. LD_{50} values were determined by Probit Analysis (Finney 1971). Means of the three replicates of treatments were tested by Tukey's method. Treatment means were compared using Fisher's LSD.

Plate 1 Spice materials

Plate 2 Management of rice weevils by different spice powders

Plate 3 Adult male and female of *Sitophilus oryzae*

Results

The study found mean mortality of rice weevils was significantly different at $p < 0.05$ ($F = 20.127$, $df = 4, 10$) and the mortality of rice weevils treated with pepper powders was higher than other powders (Figure 1 – 3 & Table 1).

The probit analyses of LD_{50} for each powder are presented in Figures 4 to 8. The result showed that the minimum dose required to attain 50% mortality of rice weevils was found in *Piper nigrum* ($LD_{50} = 0.74g$) and the maximum dose was found in *Capsicum anum* ($LD_{50} = 1.69$) (Table 2).

The mean number of adult weevils that were alive after 28 days is presented in Table 3. The results revealed that significantly higher mean number of adult weevils that were alive had

in control and the minimum mean number of rice weevils in rice grains treated with pepper had less weevils compared with the other treatments.

Figure 1 Mean mortality of adult *S. oryzae* after the treatment with 20g of different spice powders

Figure 2 Mean mortality of adult *S. oryzae* after the treatment with 30g of different spice powders

Figure 3 Mean mortality of adult *S. oryzae* after the treatment with 40g of different spice powders

Table 1 Mean mortality of *Sitophilus oryzae* against the use of different spice powders

Treatment	20g	30g	40g	Mean (%)
Chili	1.12	1.3	1.59	1.33
Pepper	2.88	3.39	3.59	3.28*
Cinnamon	1.40	1.69	2.00	1.70
Turmeric	1.40	1.69	1.95	1.68
Lemongrass	1.32	1.73	1.90	1.65
F				20.127
LSD				0.152

* significant at $p < 0.05$

Figure 4 Log concentration-probit mortality graph for chili powder against *S. oryzae*

Figure 5 Log concentration-probit mortality graph for pepper powder against *S. oryzae*

Figure 6 Log concentration-probit mortality graph for cinnamon powder against *S. oryzae*

Figure 7 Log concentration-probit mortality graph for turmeric powder against *S. oryzae*

Figure 8 Log concentration-probit mortality graph for lemon grass powder against *S. oryzae*Table 2 Probit analysis for toxicity of different spice powders on adult *S.oryzae*

Spices powders	LD ₅₀ value (g)
Chili	1.69
Pepper	0.74
Cinnamon	1.45
Turmeric	1.44
Lemon grass	1.41

Table 3 Mean number of alive weevils *S. oryzae* after 28 days

Treatment	No. of weevils		
	20g	30g	40g
Chilli	35.00±1.73	31.66±1.52	28.33±2.88
Pepper	4.00±1.00	3.66±1.15	3.33±1.15
Cinnamon	26.00±2.00	22.66±1.15	20.66±1.15
Turmeric	28.66±1.15	26.00±1.00	23.66±0.57
Lemon grass	26.66±0.57	25.33±0.57	22.33±0.57
Control	46.00±1.73	47.33±2.51	50.00±2.00

Discussion

In the present study, the effect of five spice powders was estimated for 28 days after the treatment. In general, the study found that all spice powders were affected on the mortality of rice weevils within 28 days.

Chili, lemongrass (Oyedele *et al.*, 2002, Chomchalow 2003, Parugrug and Roxas, 2008), and turmeric (Chander *et al.*, 1991) are well known to demonstrate insect repellent effects. But extracts of turmeric (*Curcuma longa*) and black pepper (*Piper nigrum*) were moderately repellent activity while extracts of lemongrass (*Cymbopogon citrates*) and dry chili (*Capsicum annum*) were weak attractant activity mentioned in the study of Ishii *et al.*, 2010.

In the present study, it was found that chili fruit powder had least affected value followed by turmeric, lemongrass and cinnamon. These spices did not cause any adverse effect on the rice weevils. This may be due to differences in methods and concentrations. After 28 days the results revealed that the minimum mean number of rice weevils in rice grains treated with pepper had less weevils compared with the other

treatments. Pepper seed powder had high toxicity effect on *S. oryzae* (LD₅₀ was 0.74g) and exhibited greater toxic effects rather than other spice powders. Pepper seed powder has a pungent smell, whose function may act as an insect pest repellent and cause the death of introduced adult rice weevils. These findings are supported by Asawalam *et al.*, 2012, Ashouri and Shayesteh 2010, and Ishii *et al.*, 2010.

Conclusion

This result suggests that pepper seed powder was comparatively more effective in controlling rice weevil *S. oryzae* than using other spices. The application of *Piper nigrum* (pepper seeds) increases adult mortality, and suppresses to some extent of the adult emergence. Moreover pepper has potential to provide grain protectant and may therefore be exploited for rice weevil control in storage grain. This is a preliminary study in a small scale and further studies will be needed to find out suitable methods and concentrations for wide scale usage.

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References

- Aitken, A.D. (1975). Insect travelers I: *Coleopteran Technological Bulletin*, 31.
- Asawalam, E. F., Ebere, U. E., Emeasor, K. C. (2012). Effect of some plant products on the control of rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) Coleoptera: Curculionidae. *Journal of Medicinal Plants Research*, 6(33) 4811 – 4814.
- Ashouri, S., Shayesteh, N. (2010). Insecticidal activities of two powdered spices, black pepper and red pepper on adults of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L.). *Mun.Ent. Zool.* 5(2):600-607.
- Aslam, M., Ali Khan, Kh., Bajwa, M.Z.H. (2002). Potency of some spices against *Callosobruchus chinensis* L. *Online Journal of Biological Sciences*, 2: 449 – 452.
- Batta, Y.A. (2004). Control of rice weevil (*Sitophilus oryzae* L., Coleoptera: Curculionidae) with various formulations of *Metarhizium anisopliae*. *Crop Protection*, 23: 103 – 108.
- Champ, B.R and Dyte, C.E. (1976). Report of the FAO global survey pesticide susceptibility of stored grain pests. Food and Agriculture Organisation. *Plant Production and Protection Series* (5).
- Chander, H., Kulkarni, S.G., Berry, S.K. (1991). Effectiveness of turmeric powder and mustard oil as protectants in stored milled rice against the rice weevil *Sitophilus oryzae*. *Int. Pest Control*, 33:94 – 97.
- Chomchalow, N. (2003). Protection of stored products with special reference to Thailand. *AU J.T.* 7(1):31-47.

- Emeasor**, K.C., Ohbuji, R.O., Emosairue, S.O. (2005). Insecticidal activity of some seed powders against *Callosobruchus maculatus* (F.) (Coleoptera: Bruchidae) on stored cowpea. *Journal of Plant Diseases and Protection*, 112: 80 – 87.
- Fields**, P.G. (2006). Effect of *Pisum sativum* fractions on the mortality and progeny production of nine stored-grain beetles. *Journal of Stored Products Research*, 42:86-96.
- Ishii**, T., Matsuzawa, H., Vairappan, C.S. (2010). Repellent activity of common spices against the rice weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch (Coleoptera, Curculionidae). *Journal of Tropical Biology and Conservation*, 7:75 – 80.
- Mahdian**, Sh.H.A., Rahman, Md.K. (2008). Insecticidal effect of some spices on *Callosobruchus maculatus* (Fabricius) in black gram seeds. (cited Shayesteh and Ashouri, 2010. Effect of four powdered spices as repellents against adults of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.), *Sitophilus granarius* (L.) and *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) in laboratory conditions. 10th International Working Conference on Stored Product Protection. *Julius-Kühn-Archiv*, 425.)
- Nadra**, H.A.M. (2006). Use of *Sesbania sesban* (L.) merr seed extracts for the protection of wheat grain against the granary weevil, *Sitophilus granarius* (L.) (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *Scientific Journal of King Faisal University (Basic and Applied Sciences)*, 7(2):121 – 135.
- Nayak**, M.K., Collins, P.J., Pavic, H. (2004). Developing fumigation protocols to manage strongly phosphine-resistant rice weevils, *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.). *Proc. Int. Conf. Controlled Atmosphere and Fumigation in Stored Products*, Gold-Coast Australia.
- Oyedele**, A.O., Gbolade, A.A., Sosan, M.B., Adewoyin, F.B., Soyelu, O.L., Orafidiya, O.O. (2002). Formulation of an effective mosquito-repellent topical product from lemongrass oil. *Phytomedicine*, 9:259 – 262.
- Parugurg**, M.L., Roxas, A.C. (2008). Insecticidal action of five plants against maize weevil, *Sitophilus zeamais* Motsch. (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). *KMITL Science and Technology Journal*, 8:24 – 38.
- Salem**, S.A., Abou-Ela, R.G., Matter, M.M., El-Kholy, M.Y. (2007). Entomocidal Effect of *Brassica napus* extracts on two store pests, *Sitophilus oryzae* (L.) and *Rhyzopertha dominica* (Fab.) (Coleoptera). *Journal of Applied Sciences Research*, 3(4):317 – 322.
- Udo**, I.O. (2005). Evaluation of the potential of some local spices as stored grain protectants against the maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* Mots (Coleoptera: Curculionidae). (In: Ashouri and Shayesteh, 2010. Insecticidal activities of two powdered spices, black pepper and red pepper on adults of *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.) and *Sitophilus granarius* (L.). *Mun.Ent.Zool.* 5(2):600 – 606.)